

SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION AND STUDY HABITS OF SENIOR HIGH STUDENTS**Alejandrino, Mara Philia R^{*1}**

Orchid Number: 0000-0002-1057-3959

Catipay, Jerico D^{*2}

Orchid Number: 0000-0003-4611-1796

Concepcion, Prince Vincent Ace T^{*3}

Orchid Number: 0000-0003-2827-3935

Flores, Sally Mae C^{*4}

Orchid Number: 0000-0002-0460-1470

Palicte, Cherry Mae D^{*5}

Orchid Number: 0000-0003-0354-0435

Seguiro, Arlene C^{*6}

Orchid Number: 0000-0002-5618-141

^{*1, 2, 3,4,5,6} University of Southeastern Philippines College of Development Management Graduate Program Mintal Campus, Davao Cityminmin_onse@yahoo.comtheinetcomputers@gmail.comprince_concepcion771988@yahoo.comfsallymaecabigquis@gmail.comchepalicte@gmail.comseguiroarlene@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

This research was conducted to determine the significant influence of social media addiction on the study habits of the senior high students in selected school of Agusan del Sur. The researchers used a descriptive correlation method of research which involved the survey of a total of 150 senior high students. Questionnaires were the research instrument used in the gathering of data and was presented to the research adviser for approval and content validity. Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and linear regression were the statistical tools used in the study. The level of social media addiction among senior high student is high and their habit is also high. There is a significant relationship between social media addiction and the study habits of senior high students. This implies that the study habit of the senior high school students is dependent on their social media addiction. The more they utilized the social media the more study habit increases. The social media addictions of the students do not significantly influence their study habits of senior high school students.

Keywords

Social media addiction, Study habits of Senior High students, Descriptive-correlational research, Agusan Del Sur, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Social media grab the attention of the students and then diverts it towards non-educational and inappropriate actions including useless chatting and extreme web surfing. Based on the above statement we can say that social media may badly affect the study habits, academic life and learning experiences of the student (Kappuswamy and Shankar, 2010). Moreover, Sheldon (2008) said that such enormous increase of the youths using social media in the world, a lot of concerns in fact cut across from parents, church leaders, politicians and educationists on the unknown effect of social media on various aspects of human life. It is therefore very important to check on the influence of social media and their academic study habit which is a very important activity for them particularly in the life of a student.

Since the learning factor that extremely influences students' academic achievement is the study habits, establishing its foundation regardless on his level of education is very important because it helps him to increase its ability to be self-directed and self-disciplined Ebele and Olofu (2017). When students have established good

study habits, they would likely to be less stressed and not anxious during exam day, thus students who also organize and adhere to their established study schedules are more confident and calmed at test-taking time and yield better grades. Ashish (2013).

Likewise, in the study conducted by students of Davao Doctors College they found out that study habits of senior high students of Davao Doctors College are affected by their time management, study environment, and use of social media, and that these factors impact their academic performance Arieta et al (2017).

However, student that spends too much time in social media and makes less time for studying their lessons which causes the decrease of point grade point averages. Only few students are aware of the academic and professional networking opportunities the sites offered (Kimberly, Jeong and Lee, 2009).

On the other hand, social media has impacted on communication, learning, research and education in general. Liccardi, Ounnas, Massey, Kinnunen, Midy & Sakar (2007) reviewed that the students are socially connected with each other for sharing their daily learning experiences and do conversation on several topics. Many established studies have shown the influence of the internet in our society nowadays. Internet has indeed revolutionized the information era with regard to sharing, speed, storage and retrieval of information in whatever form regardless of the person's whereabouts. A variety of web technologies emerged in the internet, and on technology that is creating a big impact with regard to information sharing and communication are the social media networks.

According to (Osharive, 2015), social media have positive and negative effects on teenagers primarily in high school level in the study conducted in University of Lagos in Nigeria. Negative effects contain lack of privacy, distracting students from their academic work, taking most of their productive time and sometimes they tend to develop an aggressive or violent behavior towards family, peers, and their social circle. On the other hand, positive effects such as forming online communities in order to plan for a project, have group discussions about class material or use of social networking sites as a way to keep in contact when a student who has been absent needs to be updated on current academic information have benefits if used appropriately. This only shows that technology is evolving at a very fast rate and its effect is very apparent in the current generation. But as it is, technology like two sides of a coin, bring with it both negative and positive sides.

In a study conducted in a state university in Iloilo, the results showed that the respondents study habits and academic performance were to a high extent influenced by social networking. Most likely that this high influence may have been result of easy access to and brought about by accessibility of gadgets like Smartphone's and other electronic devices with mobile data and Wi-Fi connection. The affordability and availability of these gadgets in the market may have been another reason (Judilla and Gemora, 2015).

The above mentioned scenario spurred interest of the researchers to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level social media addiction to the level study habits of the selected senior high school students in Agusan Del Sur.

FRAMEWORK

According to Straubhaar et al (2014) uses and gratifications perspectives dominates thinking about social media consumption and behavior. This theory assumes active audience. In other words users actively seek out media that meet their needs for knowledge, social interaction, and diversion. They further argued that it is possible to become so deeply involved with our favorite media activity that it acts like an addictive drug. It is within this premise that this addiction can influence the study habits of students.

Olutola, et al (2016) conducted a study on the use of social media and study habits of students and found out that there is significant relationship which implies that the utilization of social media is positively related to study habits and that the more the use of social media, the better is the students study habits.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted to identify the level of social media addiction in terms of technology pros, usage duration, heavy users, and social pressures; to identify the level of study habits of senior high students in terms of time management, study environment, task taking, note taking skills, reading skills, and writing skills; to determine if there is a significant relationship between social media addiction and study habits of senior high students, and to identify if social media addiction significantly influence the study habits of senior high students.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive correlational method of research was used in this study. This design is appropriate in determining the relationship between social media addiction and the study habits of senior high students in selected school of Agusan del Sur. There were 150 senior high students as sample respondents using purposive or convenience sampling. Questionnaires were the research instrument used in the gathering of data and was presented to the research adviser for approval and content validity. The researchers personally administered the questionnaires to the respondents. The respondents answered the survey questionnaire for confidentiality of data to comply with the research ethics protocol. Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlational and linear regression was the statistical tool used in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented in this section are the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered to answer the questions raised in the study.

Level of Social Media Addiction among Senior High School Students

Presented in Table I is the level of social media addiction of senior high students and they reveal high level with a mean rating of 3.54. This means that the senior high school students often used social media as means of communication. However, they are sometimes engrossed in using internet. This findings affirm with Liccardi, Ounnas, Massey, Kinnunen, Midy & Sakar (2007) that social media has impacted on communication, learning, research and education in general.

Moreover, *Technology Pros* as indicator are rated with the mean of 4.03 or high level this finding affirms Lusk (2010) that social media can yield many benefits for the young especially students because of its ability to enhance connections by making them easily accessible. Moreover, *Usage Duration* garnered a mean rating of 3.81 or high level. *Heavy Users* with the mean of 2.96 or moderate level and *Social Pressures* with the mean of 3.34 denotes a moderate level.

Table I Level of Social Media Addiction among Senior High School Students

Social Media Addiction	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Technology Pros	0.70	4.03	High
Usage Duration	0.77	3.81	High
Heavy Users	1.09	2.96	Moderate
Social Pressures	0.99	3.34	Moderate
Overall	0.71	3.54	High

Level of Study Habits of Senior High School Students

Presented in Table 2 is the level of study habits of senior high school students and they revealed high level with the mean rating 3.81. This means that they often manage their time despite their exposure to social media. Thus, their study habits was already established that makes them more confident and calmed in test-taking Ashish (2013).

All indicators of study habits are rated high level. Time management has a mean rating mean of 3.74 , *study environment* with the mean of 3.62, *task taking* with a mean of 3.61, *note taking skills* with a mean of 3.97, *reading skills* with a mean of 3.99, and *writing skills* with a mean of 3.95 respectively in which confirm to the study conducted of Arieta et al (2017) that study habits of senior high students are affected by those above mentioned factors as well as the use of social media, and that these factors impact their academic performance.

Table 2. Level of Study Habits of Senior High School Students

Study Habits	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Time Management	0.64	3.74	High
Study Environment	0.77	3.62	High
Task Taking	0.75	3.61	High
Note Taking Skills	0.85	3.97	High
Reading Skills	0.73	3.99	High
Writing Skills	0.63	3.95	High
Overall	0.56	3.81	High

Significant Relationship between Social Media Addiction and Study Habits

Presented in Table 3 is the significant relationship between social media addiction and the study habits of senior high students as revealed in the overall r computed value of .165 with the p value .044 which is less than .05 level of significance. This supports to study of Olutola, et al (2016) that the utilization of the students on social media is dependent on their social media addiction that the more the use of social media the better is the students study habits developed.

Among indicators of social media addiction, only usage duration significantly relate to study habits with the r computed of .178 and p value .030 which is less than .05 level of significance. This implies that the more they utilize the social media the more their study habit increases Olutola, et al (2016). However, other indicators such technology pros, heavy users, and social pressures do not show significant relationship to study habit.

Table 3. Relationship Between Social Media Addiction and Study Habit of Senior High School Student

		TM	SE	TTPS	NTS	RS	WS	overall
Technology Pros	Pearson Correlation	.130	.026	.121	-.028	.140	.216**	.125
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.113	.756	.139	.731	.088	.008	.128
Usage Duration	Pearson Correlation	.112	.036	.120	.082	.222**	.268**	.178*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.174	.660	.144	.321	.006	.001	.030
Heavy Users	Pearson Correlation	.167*	.072	.165*	-.046	.062	.096	.105
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	.382	.043	.578	.449	.243	.200
Personality Disorder	Pearson Correlation	.216**	.062	.147	-.004	.093	.187*	.145
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	.454	.072	.965	.256	.022	.077
Overall	Pearson Correlation	.199*	.063	.172*	-.007	.146	.225**	.165*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	.441	.036	.932	.075	.006	.044

Presented in Table 4 is the non-significant influence of the social media addiction of the study habits of the senior high school students as revealed in the F value of 1.310 with the P value of .269 which is greater than .05 level of significance. The result is not significance and the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that social media addiction has nothing to do with the study habits of senior high school students.

The r square value is .035 which means that the overall influence of the social media addiction is only 3.5% to the study habit. The variance of 96.5% is attributed to other factors not covered in the study. None of the indicators of social media addiction singly influence the study habits as revealed in the regression equation $Y = 3.286 + .007 X1 + .098 X2 + .005 X3 + .033 X4$ which means that in the absence of social media addiction the study habits has the constant of 3.286 equivalent to moderate level.

Table 4. Influence of Social Media Addiction on the Study Habits of Senior High School Students

Social Media Addiction	Study Habits			
	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision on Ho
1. Technology Pros (X1)	.007	.086	.931	Not Significant
2. Usage Duration (X2)	.098	1.249	.214	Not Significant
3. Heavy Users (X3)	.005	.094	.926	Not Significant
4. Personality Disorder (X3)	.033	.480	.632	Not Significant
R Square	.035	3.5%		
F Value	1.310			
P Value	.269			
Regression Equation	$Y = 3.286 + .007 X1 + .098 X2 + .005 X3 + .033 X4$			

CONCLUSION

Based from the findings, the researchers concluded that the level of social media addiction was high, and the level of study habits of senior high students is high. Moreover, there is no significant relationship between the level of social media addiction to the level of study habits of senior high students. This affirms with the concept

of Olutola, et al (2016) stated that there is significant relationship between students level use of social media and study habits. Thus, student level of use of social media is positively related to study habit. Social media addictions do not significantly influence on the study habits of the senior high school students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kuppaswamy, S., & Narayan, P. (2010). The Impact of Social Networking Websites on the Education of Youth. *International Journal of Virtual Communities and Social Networking (IJVCSN)*, 2(1), 67-79.
- [2] Ebele Uju F. and Olofu Paul A. (2017) Study habit and its impact on secondary school students' academic performance in biology in the Federal Capital Territory, Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja, Nigeria. Vol. 12(10), pp. 583-588, 23 May, 2017 DOI: 10.5897/ERR2016.3117 Article Number: 734608A64524
- [3] Ashish R (2013). Study Habits for Students: Bad Ones to Avoid, Good Ones to Achieve Success. www.education.wisc.edu/education/soe/newsevents. 12/3/2016
- [4] Arieta, Kaye Marie D.Gementiza, Roda C.Saco, Cielo Jabe D. (2017) Actors affecting study habits on the academic performance of senior high school students of davao doctors college pp. 3
- [5] Kim, Y., Jeong, O., & Lee, S. (in press). On social web sites. *Information Systems: Creation, Management, and Utilization*. Retrieved November 9, 2009, from Science Direct database.
- [6] Liccardi, I., Ounnas, A., Pau, R., Massey, E., Kinnunen, P., Lewthwaite, S., ... Sarkar, C. (2007). The role of social networks in students' learning experiences. *ACM SIGCSE Bulletin*, 39(4), 224-237.
- [7] Osharive, P. (2015). Social media and academic performance of students, conference paper of January 2015. Retrieved September, 2016 from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273765340>.
- [8] Judilla, A., Gemora, R.(2015). Influence of Social Networking on the Study Habits and Performance of Students in a State University. *Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 1(2).1-12
- [9] Lusk, B. (2010). Digital natives and social media behaviors: An overview. *Prevention Researcher*, 173-6.